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CHANGES IN GENERAL BLOOD PARAMETERS DURING ACUTE CYTOMEGALOVIRUS AND HERPES INFECTIONS

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Abstract

Opportunistic infections (OIs) are mainly observed in individuals with weakened immune systems - particularly those carrying the Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), transplant recipients, or patients receiving immunosuppressive therapy due to chronic illnesses. These infections cause various changes in the hematological system. For the study, blood samples were taken from patients who applied to the clinical laboratory of the V.Y. Akhundov Scientific-Research Institute of Medical Prophylaxis. Antibodies formed in individuals infected with opportunistic infections were determined using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) method, employing test kits produced by the "Vector Best" company. The studies were carried out using a semi-automatic Stat Fax 4700 analyzer. The absolute and relative counts of lymphocytes and leukocytes in the blood were evaluated based on hemogram indicators. The article scientifically analyzes the main blood parameters - such as hemoglobin, leukocytes, lymphocytes, platelets, C-reactive protein (CRP), and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and their changes during opportunistic infections. These alterations are diagnostically and prognostically significant and play an important role in monitoring treatment.

Keywords: opportunistic infections, immune system, monocytes, lymphocytes, CRP, neutrophils

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Introduction

The problem of opportunistic infections is increasingly becoming a pressing issue of modern times. This is associated with a number of factors that weaken the immune system, including the growing incidence of chronic diseases treated with immunosuppressive drugs. Opportunistic infections are caused by numerous microorganisms - bacteria, fungi, parasites, and viruses. In most cases, these microorganisms cause asymptomatic infections in healthy individuals; however, when the immune system is weakened, they can lead to life-threatening infections. These infections can cause certain changes in the hematological system. During opportunistic infections, variations can occur in blood parameters such as hemoglobin, leukocytes, lymphocytes, neutrophils, platelets, and CRP. Other immune cells such as B lymphocytes and monocytes also play an important role in the immune response against opportunistic infections. It has been determined that in individuals with HIV/AIDS, B cells have a reduced ability to produce antibodies against opportunistic pathogens. Studies have also shown that monocytes in HIV/AIDS patients have a diminished capacity to engulf and destroy opportunistic pathogens (Komori et al., 2015; Ram et al., 2010). Platelets are among the most common blood components. Their role in innate and adaptive immune responses during various types of infections has been investigated (Lagrou et al., 2009). In opportunistic infections, platelets have been found to interact with neutrophils, monocytes, and dendritic cells, indicating a close relationship with the immune system. Unlike the absolute counts of platelets or lymphocytes, the Platelet-Lymphocyte Ratio (PLR) is a more valuable indicator for predicting various inflammatory conditions (Thakur et al., 2021). PLR has been confirmed as a novel inflammatory marker associated with tumors, coronary heart disease, and connective tissue diseases. In immunocompetent hosts, infection with *T. gondii* triggers a complex innate and adaptive immune response that allows the parasite to persist long-term (Ssentongo et al., 2021). The role of lymphocytes in *T. gondii* infection lies in limiting parasite reactivation during the chronic phase.

Materials and Methods

For the study, blood samples were collected from patients who applied to the clinical laboratory of the V.Y. Akhundov Scientific-Research Institute of Medical Prophylaxis.

Antibodies formed in individuals infected with opportunistic infections were determined using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) method, employing test kits produced by the "Vector Best" company (Prince et al., 2014). The analyses were carried out using a Stat Fax 4700 semi-automatic analyzer. The absolute and relative counts of lymphocytes and leukocytes in the blood were evaluated based on hemogram indicators (Bal et al., 2012). The study examined white blood cells (WBC), neutrophils (NEU), lymphocytes (LYM), monocytes (MON), platelets (PLT), hemoglobin (HB), and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR). A total of 238 patients who applied to the clinical laboratory between January 2024 and November 2024 were included in the study, and their blood parameters were analyzed.

Purpose and Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the changes occurring in certain blood parameters of individuals infected with opportunistic infections.

To achieve this goal, the following objectives were carried out:

- Determination of the levels of M immunoglobulins in individuals with opportunistic infections.
- Examination of changes in certain blood parameters among individuals who tested seropositive for IgM.

Results

The research was conducted in the following directions:

The seropositivity of individuals infected with opportunistic infections was tested using the ELISA method (Le Balc'h et al., 2020). During these infections, changes in certain peripheral blood parameters (leukocytes, lymphocytes, neutrophils, platelets, etc.) and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were examined. The seropositivity rates for opportunistic infections and the levels of Immunoglobulin G (IgG) and Immunoglobulin M (IgM) were analyzed in a total of 238 examined individuals. Among them, 9% (27 individuals) were seropositive for toxoplasmosis, 38% (122 individuals) for cytomegalovirus (CMV), 33% (102 individuals) for HSV-1, and 20% (62 individuals) for mixed infections (Herpes I IgG + CMV IgG) (Ishibashi et al., 2008; James et al., 2020). As shown in Figure 1, the distribution of infection types is illustrated below.

Figure 1. Distribution of opportunistic infections among 238 individuals.

Blood parameters compared included leukocytes, lymphocyte percentages, lymphocyte counts, neutrophil percentages

and counts, monocyte percentages and counts, platelet levels (PLT), CRP, and ESR. Statistical significance levels were

indicated with asterisks.

In the CMV IgM group, statistically significant differences were observed in leukocyte count, lymphocyte percentage, neutrophil percentage, and CRP levels compared to the control group. The leukocyte level in the CMV IgM group (7.7 ± 1.2) was higher than in the control group (6.5 ± 1.0), while in the Herpes IgM group (7.28 ± 1.1), the difference was smaller.

The lymphocyte percentage was highest in the CMV IgM group (40.7 ± 5.1), indicating increased immune cell activity. In contrast, this parameter was significantly lower in the Herpes IgM group (29.9 ± 4.3), suggesting alterations in immune

balance.

The neutrophil percentage was highest in the Herpes IgM group (60.8 ± 5.3) compared to the control group (49 ± 4.5) and the CMV IgM group (49.8 ± 4.2).

The CRP level was also highest in the Herpes IgM group (30 ± 2), indicating stronger inflammatory processes. The ESR parameter was elevated in both the Herpes IgM and CMV IgM groups compared to the control group. As summarized in Table 1, the comparison of major blood indicators demonstrates these statistical differences among groups.

Table 1. Some parameters of general blood analysis in IgM seropositive individuals

General blood indicators	CMV IgM (n=27)	Herpes IgM (n=10)	Control group (n=16)
Leukocytes	$7.7 \pm 1.2^*$	7.28 ± 1.1	6.5 ± 1.0
Lymphocytes %	40.7 ± 5.1	$29.9 \pm 4.3^{***}$	40.35 ± 5.2
Lymphocyte count	$3.15 \pm 0.5^*$	2.14 ± 0.4	2.67 ± 0.5
Neutrophils %	49.8 ± 4.2	$60.8 \pm 5.3^{***}$	49 ± 4.5
Neutrophil count	$3.85 \pm 0.6^*$	4.5 ± 0.7	3.22 ± 0.5
Monocytes %	6.6 ± 0.8	6.68 ± 0.7	7.1 ± 0.9
Monocyte count	$0.34 \pm 0.05^*$	$0.59 \pm 0.06^*$	0.46 ± 0.05
PLT	273 ± 15	290 ± 18	291 ± 20
CRP	5 ± 1	$30 \pm 2^{***}$	5 ± 1
ESR	22 ± 3	26 ± 4	12 ± 2

Note: *, **, *** - Statistical significance compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$).

In the CMV IgM group, leukocyte levels were higher compared to the control group. The lymphocyte percentage was highest in the CMV IgM group and lowest in the Herpes IgM group.

The CRP level was the highest among all parameters in the Herpes IgM group. These differences are visually represented in Figure 2 and Figure 3, which illustrate the variations in general blood indicators and inflammatory markers among the study groups.

Herpes IgM group. These differences are visually represented in Figure 2 and Figure 3, which illustrate the variations in general blood indicators and inflammatory markers among the study groups.

Figure 2. Comparison of leukocyte, lymphocyte, neutrophil, monocyte, CRP, and ESR levels among CMV IgM, Herpes IgM, and control groups.

Figure 3. Percentage comparison of neutrophils, lymphocytes, and platelet (PLT) values in CMV IgM, Herpes IgM, and control groups.

Discussion

The results of this study examined the impact of infections on blood parameters and identified changes observed in the hematological indicators of different groups. When compared with previous studies, both similarities and differences were revealed. In particular, comparisons with studies conducted in different countries suggest that these variations may be related to regional, genetic, and environmental factors (Suzich and Cliffe, 2018). A study conducted in China (Parry et al., 2016) reported that CRP levels doubled during CMV infection compared to healthy individuals. In that study, the CRP level was recorded as 20 ± 2 , whereas in our study, CRP was 21.8 ± 0.45 among individuals with CMV IgG positivity. Regarding toxoplasmosis infections, the existing literature, particularly (Ssentongo et al., 2021), emphasized that WBC levels slightly increase during toxoplasmosis, though they may vary depending on the stage of infection. The findings reaffirm that infections have multifaceted effects on blood parameters, and different pathogens exhibit specific influences (Leruez-Ville et al., 2024).

The results obtained indicate that while the effect of infections on blood parameters is universal, this influence can vary across countries depending on social, genetic, and environmental factors.

Future research is essential to examine these differences in more detail and to conduct international comparative studies.

This study provides important insights for understanding the effects of infections on blood parameters and for improving diagnostic approaches.

Conclusion

The study examined seropositivity for opportunistic infections (toxoplasmosis, simple herpes, HSV1, and cytomegalovirus) and immunoglobulin G (IgG) and immunoglobulin M (IgM) levels in 238 individuals. Among all examined subjects, 9% (27 individuals) were seropositive for *Toxoplasma*, 38% (122 individuals) for Cytomegalovirus, 33% (102 individuals) for HSV1, and 20% (62 individuals) for mixed infections. The study results show that various infections cause noticeable changes in blood parameters, and these changes differ depending on the type, stage, and chronicity of the infection (Kapsenberg et al., 1970; Lagrou et al., 2009).

- Individuals who tested seropositive for CMV IgM and HSV1 IgM infections had higher leukocyte and neutrophil percentages than the control group.

- The lymphocyte percentage was significantly lower in the Herpes IgM group compared to the control group, while it was higher in the CMV IgM group.

- The monocyte percentage showed an increase in the IgM groups.

- Platelet levels did not show any significant change.

- The ESR parameter was significantly higher in the HSV1 IgM group.

This study provides new data for understanding how infections affect blood parameters. Furthermore, these results have practical significance for improving diagnostic, therapeutic, and preventive approaches.

Future studies aim to explore the mechanisms of infection effects in more depth and conduct research on larger populations.

The findings reaffirm that infections have multifaceted effects on blood parameters, and different pathogens exhibit specific influences.

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